

Agency theory and international climate change financing accountability regimes

Author: Rishi Basak

Affiliations: Rishi Basak, Wageningen University, Consortium of International Agricultural Research Centers and Policy Research International

rishibasak@hotmail.com, rbasak@policyresearch.ca, +52 595 102 1627.

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Affiliations: Rishi Basak, Wageningen University, Consortium of International Agricultural Research Centers and Policy Research International

Corresponding author coordinates: rishibasak@hotmail.com, rbasak@policyresearch.ca, +52 595 102 1627.

Abstract This paper uses agency theory to analyze the incentives that donors (principal) and recipients (agent) face as actors in an accountability regime for the financing of international climate change mitigation and adaptation actions in developing countries. We look at a specific set of formal and informal accountability measures that serve to align the incentives of the donor with those of the recipient. These measures include the use of performance indicators, the institution of an accreditation system for potential recipients, the imposition of penalties for poor performance, as well as the role of pressure exerted by civil society organizations (CSO). We find that asymmetric information can increase the risk of low project performance. We show that formal accountability procedures such as ex ante accreditation and ex post penalties can influence recipient behavior and have a positive impact on project outcomes, but that such measures impose risks upon the agent, which could lead him to decide not to take on the climate change project. CSO pressure was found to motivate donors and recipients to become more efficient and effective in their delivery of climate change projects. We also discuss how the risk profile of a given project can have a bearing on the accountability measures the principal can impose upon her agent.

Keywords Principal-agent, climate change, accountability, climate finance, penalties, performance indicators.

1 Introduction

The Long Term Financing under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) has set a goal of raising \$100 billion per year by 2020 (UNFCCC 2014). This goal was reiterated at the 21st Conference of the Parties of the UNFCCC (COP 21) held in Paris in December 2015, where 195 nations signed the Paris Agreement, in which the Conference of the Parties of the UNFCCC requested “*expedite(d) support for the least developed countries and other developing country Parties for the formulation of national adaptation plans*” (UNFCCC 2015, p.7) and recognized the “*importance of adequate and predictable financial resources...*” (UNFCCC 2015, p.8).

Expectations about the follow-up to COP 21 and the broader post-Kyoto international climate change process are high, especially with respect to the financing mechanisms for climate change mitigation and adaptation in developing countries. One of these “great expectations” is that a strong accountability regime be put in place to manage the allocation of these significant sums (Abbott and Gartner 2011; Bird et al. 2011; van Kerkhoff et al. 2011). The term “accountability regime” is used here to describe the system of management that is put in place to ensure accountability, where accountability is construed as: “*(A) relationship between an actor and a forum, in which the actor has an obligation to explain and to justify his or her conduct, the forum can pose questions and pass judgement, and the actor may face consequences.*” (Bovens 2007, p. 450). Ultimately, accountability regimes serve to legitimize the institutions involved (Kersbergen and Waarden 2004) and are often taken as a proxy for good governance (Dubnick 1998).

Similar and related to the role of the enforcement of property rights, accountability regimes allow economic actors to transact in a way that better satisfies all actors involved and helps provide added certainty to transactions by spelling out expectations, roles and responsibilities, as well as mechanisms to give account and face consequences for not complying with agreed-upon objectives. The impact of accountability regimes in achieving desired objectives has been documented in studies in various fields. For instance, Skrla et al. (2001) argue that examples of good educational outcomes in the United States tend to be found in school districts in states equipped with strong accountability regimes. Thurnher (2008), who analyzed the impact of the accountability regime for American private security contractors during the Iraq war, identified several weaknesses in the regime (e.g., screening and training programs, investigations and prosecutions for contractor misconduct) that hurt the counterinsurgency efforts. More germane to this paper, the World Bank (2004) found that service delivery failures in developing countries were related to weak accountability and that this was negatively impacting the poor. Anderson and Feder (2004) found weak accountability in the form of misaligned incentives of agricultural extension workers, where extension services were held accountable for the budget they spent and other activity-level indicators, but were not accountable for making sure that their programs benefited farmers.

This paper will look at the incentives that donors and recipients face in the financing of climate change mitigation and adaptation actions in developing countries, as actors in an accountability regime. The generic “donor-recipient” relationship analyzed in this paper can represent specific cases, such as the relationship between the Green Climate Fund (GCF) and one of its so-called “Accredited Entities”, but can also be transposed to any relationship between a donor (bilateral or multilateral) and a recipient (e.g., developing country, implementing agency) involved in climate change adaptation and mitigation efforts.

This paper therefore addresses the following question: What accountability measures serve to align the incentives of the donor with those of the recipient in climate change financing? In order to answer the question, we frame the problem as a principal-agent relationship, which allows us to assess the impact of various accountability measures introduced in climate change financing modalities and determine how these can affect the “contract” between the donor and recipient. This also allows us to determine the potential impact of certain agent characteristics, such as their prudence and risk preferences, on the donor-recipient relationship.

This is in keeping with other authors, such as Steinberg (2010), Kluvers & Tippett (2010) and Haque (2014), who have looked at accountability relationships in public administration using agency theory.¹ However, the extant literature offers limited insights into the specific accountability measures found in international climate change financing institutions, which is our objective with this paper.

The paper is organized as follows: The next section elaborates on the concept of accountability as a principal-agent relationship and describes the accountability issues stemming from the relationship between donor and recipient in international climate change financing. We then analyze the impact of information asymmetry and the use of imperfect performance data, as well as the use of formal and informal accountability mechanisms (i.e., an accreditation process, penalties and pressure from civil society organizations) to align the agent’s incentives with that of the principal. This is followed by a discussion of the impact of agent risk preferences. The last section of the paper provides concluding remarks, suggestions for policy-makers to improve the accountability relationship between donors and recipients in climate change financing, as well as areas for further research.

2 Accountability as a principal-agent relationship

Accountability is a relationship between at least two individuals - one giving account to the other. Principal-agent problems (also known as agency dilemmas and agency theory) occur when a “principal” (i.e., any person, organization or other entity) uses an “agent” (again, any person, organization or entity) to fulfil an action on her behalf. The dilemma occurs when the agent, who acts in self-interest, has motivations that are not well aligned with those of the principal and the principal cannot directly observe the agent’s actions (Rees 1985). Another element of the principal-agent problem is that of adverse selection, which is when an agent hides the fact that he may not have the skills required to deliver results as per the principal’s expectation (i.e., uncertainty about quality) (Akerlof 1970). These agency problems arise in multiple contexts where responsibility is delegated and are very likely to be present in the the accountability relationship between donors and recipients in the context of international climate change financing (e.g., the GCF providing project funding to an implementing agency, a donor country providing bilateral funding to a developing country to implement a national adaptation plan).

Agency theory has been used to study a multitude of public policy and market issues, from energy consumption (Jaffe and Stavins 1994) to professional sports (Purcell 2009). A great number of authors have used agency theory to analyze public accountability, as it offers “*a flexible framework for modeling innumerable variations in institutional arrangements, and*

¹ For an overview of the contribution of principal-agent modeling to the study of accountability, please see Gailmard (2014).

comparing their potential for inducing desirable behavior by agents.” (Gailmard, 2014, p. 2).

For our purposes, we use agency theory to analyze the accountability issues stemming from the relationship between a donor and recipient in international climate change financing, where the donor is interested in structuring the terms and conditions of a grant agreement to ensure that the grantee will use the financing in a way that is agreeable to the donor. To do so, the donor puts in place an accountability regime, including accountability measures such as the pre-screening of applicants, imposing a monitoring scheme and penalties for poor performance, which all create “incentive bundles” that the agent becomes subject to and that in turn influence the agent’s behavior, in accordance with the objectives of the donor/principal, who holds the agent to account. These incentive bundles can be ex ante or ex post accountability measures, as described below.

Certain accountability measures are put in place prior to (i.e., ex ante) any work being undertaken or even before any money has been transferred between donor and recipient (e.g., pre-screening potential grant recipients). Other accountability measures take effect only after (i.e., ex post) the transfer of money and the expending of effort by the recipient has taken place (e.g., penalties). This terminology has been used in a similar fashion by other authors, namely Bovens (2007) and Soudry (2008).

Another important consideration in accountability relationships is that of the information available to the principal to ensure that she can hold her agent to account (Bovens 2007). When a donor makes an investment in a grant project or program, she requires information about the performance of her investment, using various performance indicators and corresponding metrics (Adam and Gunning 2002; Morra-Imas and Rist 2009). The quality of the performance information, including performance indicators, will have a bearing on the decisions made by the various actors involved (Mosley, Hudson, and Verschoor 2004; Holzapfel 2016), including the ability to hold actors to account. As such, informational issues will also be analyzed to see how these can affect the ability to resolve the principal-agent problem.

3 Informational issues

In a classic principal-agent model, the principal uses a compensation scheme to incentivize her agent in striving for high levels of performance. The principal strives to develop a compensation package that will maximize her utility U_P , based on the agent’s behavior, or actions, under this payment scheme. The agent, on the other hand, will put in a level of effort that will maximize his utility U_A , based on this compensation package (i.e., taking the compensation package as given). This applies to many cases in the climate change financing context, where the donor has a pre-established amount for grants.² The principal therefore needs to design an offer to the agent in a way that motivates him to exert a high enough level of effort (e). The principal’s utility increases with higher levels of effort by the agent and decreases as she pays higher compensation payments, $y(e)$, to her agent. The agent, on the other hand, has a utility function that is affected by the effort he expends, e , and the compensation payment, $y(e)$, he receives by the principal. U_A is decreasing in effort and increasing in y .

The agent is willing to undertake work for the principal, as long as the payment scheme she offers (minus the effort he needs to expend to fulfil his contract) is at least equal to his

² It must be noted that there are also many instances where donors publish open calls for proposals with no specified grant amounts. In those cases, the initial compensation payment is proposed by the agent.

reservation utility U_{OA} , which is the utility he would obtain from his next best employment (or leisure) option (i.e., $U_A(y, e) \geq U_{OA}$). As many authors have demonstrated, if the principal were able to directly observe the agent's level of effort, then she could simply offer him a fixed wage that would allow the agent to reach his reservation utility, no more, no less (Kreps 1990; Laffont and Martimort 2009). However, it is difficult to imagine a set of circumstances in international climate change financing where the donor would have the ability to directly and perfectly observe the recipient's level of effort. This is indeed the crux of the principal-agent problem.

With the agent possessing private information regarding his level of effort, the principal is now unwilling to bear all the risk associated with the achievement of climate change mitigation and adaptation results for the project she intends to finance. One way to indirectly gauge the agent's level of effort is via the imposition of a Monitoring and Evaluation System (MES). The MES would require the agent to develop performance indicators, as well as collect and report performance data to the principal. These project performance indicators would be at the activity, output and outcome levels, which is reflective of modern donor requirements and grant management practices (Adam and Gunning 2002; Crawford and Bryce 2003). In modern aid project management, grantees are required to develop MESs that usually set out what indicators are to be used for project monitoring. In the case of the GCF, this is set out in the Monitoring and Accountability Framework for Accredited Entities (Green Climate Fund 2015). Once the MES is approved by the donor, the agent begins project implementation and collects data to produce the metrics for the indicators. This information is then put into a progress report and shared with the donor, who in turn reviews and scrutinizes the information therein. The development and implementation of the MES, including data collection, reporting and review, is costly to the principal and the agent.

The activity indicator (α) represents a set of activities that the grantee has completed in the context of the implementation of the project financed by the donor (e.g., number of events organized, number of collaborations with partners, policy dialogues undertaken). The output indicator (φ) can be thought of as including items such as the number of people trained, or number of publications produced by the grant recipient.³ The outcome indicator (θ) would be composed of a metric for greenhouse gas mitigation and adaptation and should be construed as an imperfect indicator, as many authors have shown that climate change indicators, especially adaptation metrics, are difficult to obtain (Adger et al. 2005; Branca et al. 2012; Engle 2011).

The donor's imposition of the MES gives her more assurance that the agent is not shirking, but this comes at a cost (disutility) to both players. Tracking these indicators is costlier to the agent, as it is the agent who is required to design, collect data for, and report on these indicators, whereas the principal only faces the cost of reviewing the indicators and the corresponding metrics reported by the agent on a regular basis. So now that the agent's utility is negatively affected by the cost of developing and implementing the MES, the agent requires a higher payment to make sure that the contract indeed brings about utility that is greater or equal to his reservation utility U_{OA} . Similarly, the principal, now facing this new cost, can only maintain her same level of utility if the agent produces a higher level of performance and/or if she reduces the payment she provides him.

³ For further examples of activity-level and output-level indicators, as well as a good discussion on their appropriate design and use, please see Bourne et al. (2000); Morra-Imas and Rist (2009); and Schiavo-Campo (1999). As Ebrahim (2003) mentions, it is important to avoid falling into the trap of choosing easily measurable (but not necessarily appropriate) indicators in order to please donors.

The principal can decide to pay her agent based solely on the climate change indicator θ reported by her agent (i.e., $y(\theta)$), while imposing the reporting of the other elements of the MES (i.e., indicators of activities and outputs) for accountability purposes only. Alternatively, the principal could choose to pay her agent based on θ and the indicators of activities and outputs (i.e., $y(\theta, \alpha, \varphi)$). This would provide some compensation to the agent for the cost of developing and implementing the MES, but would also make the principal face a greater y to pay to the agent (as $y(\theta, \alpha, \varphi) > y(\theta)$, unless the agent delivers zero α and φ). For this scheme to make sense to the principal, paying the agent for α and φ needs to lead to levels of θ that bring about utility to the principal that outweigh this additional payment. If the addition of α and φ to the agent's payment scheme does not lead to large enough increases in θ , then the principal is better off with the previous scheme (i.e., imposing the tracking of α and φ for accountability purposes, but not providing additional payment for performance related to activities and outputs).⁴

In other words, the stronger the positive correlation between α , φ and θ (i.e., the more activities and outputs are thought to bring about improvements in climate change mitigation and adaptation results), the greater the benefit to the principal of paying her agent for α , φ , in addition to θ . However, if the correlation is weak, or worse, spurious (i.e., if outside factors have a significant influence on the achievement of θ), then the principal will be overpaying the agent with such a motivational amount.⁵

This reflects the pragmatic challenge of choosing appropriate performance indicators and of testing a project or program's corresponding "theory of change". Theories of change are models of the contribution of initiatives to intended results, made up of a logical chain of activities, outputs and outcomes (Serrat 2013). Some authors have noted the important difference between theories of change and other similar tools (for example, impact pathways, logic models), which is the inclusion of assumptions about the causal links between activities, outputs and outcomes (Chen 2015; Mayne 2015). Ensuring that the activities and outputs being tracked are indeed contributing to the outcomes targeted by the project or program (e.g., through periodic performance data collection and statistical analysis) is therefore crucial in setting up a well-functioning contract between the donor and recipient.

In the next section, we look at non-monetary mechanisms that can serve to motivate the agent, namely formal accountability measures that can be imposed upon the agent.

4 Formal accountability measures

The first formal accountability measure to be analyzed is an ex ante accreditation process for the agent. This accreditation process would impose a series of specific requirements to be met by the agent before he is considered for funding, to ensure the agent has mechanisms in place for sound project management. Such a pre-screening process is used by many multilateral institutions and is a key component of the accountability regimes of the GEF and the GCF, for instance.

Another accountability measure to consider is the penalties donors can impose on grant recipients with unsatisfactory performance (Binnendijk 2000; Collier et al. 1997). For instance,

⁴ For a mathematical treatment on the value of additional performance measures in principal-agent relationships, please see Feltham and Xie (1994).

⁵ For a discussion and mathematical treatment on the use of correlated performance information to improve contracting, please see Laffont and Martimort (2009).

the GCF, as part of the contract it enters upon with its grant recipients, has the ability to withhold payments, downgrade or withdraw an entity's accreditation status, or "blacklist" poor performers (Green Climate Fund 2015). These could also be thought of as "clawbacks" on the grant payment, that is, the ability of the donor to ask for a certain amount of money back if performance is judged to be insufficient.⁶

Accreditation would provide utility to the principal, as it would give her a greater assurance that her agent is suitable to undertake the tasks at hand, but would provide disutility to the agent, as it entails a significant cost. As the agent needs to go through accreditation prior to even knowing if he will be offered a contract by the principal, the accreditation cost is borne *ex ante*, based on the implied probability that a contract will indeed be offered.

It must be noted that in international climate change financing, institutions such as the GEF and GCF invite several institutions to seek accreditation. As such, once accredited, this gives these entities oligopoly power, as it limits the number of players who can apply for climate change project funding (as only accredited entities can apply for funding), driving up the price agents can fetch, compared to a fully open system without this barrier to entry.

Similarly, penalties imposed by the principal increase her utility, but provide disutility to the agent. So what do accreditation and penalties mean for accountability? Accreditation reduces the risk of project failure (by reducing the risk of adverse selection) and increases the transparency via additional reporting requirements (i.e., information about the management "competency" of the agent obtained via the accreditation package submitted by the agent). The implementation of penalties (or the fear of facing them) also incentivizes greater performance by the agent. But the principal needs to be careful with the amount of risk it transfers over to her agent via accreditation and penalties, as it may lead him to refuse the contract (Laffont and Martimort 2009; Shavell 1979).⁷

In the next section, we discuss an informal accountability measure, namely civil society organization (CSO) pressure, and analyze whether it can serve to further promote accountability.

5 Informal accountability measure

In addition to formal accountability measures, such as the accreditation process and the penalty scheme described above, informal measures also exist. Newell (2015), for instance, explored accountability and the pressure exerted by various civil society groups on key international climate change actors. This pressure can incentivize the donor and recipient to expend more efforts in reaching good results to avoid negative press and public embarrassment.

In the case of large multilateral institutions providing climate change financing, such as the World Bank, the GEF and the GCF, it is easy to imagine CSOs targeting them via various means to pressure these institutions into financing projects that align with the CSOs' values and objectives. As such, this pressure would provide disutility to the principal. If the agent is a smaller entity, such as a local non-governmental organization, it may "fly under the radar" and

⁶ The accreditation process and penalty scheme are akin to premiums and deductibles present in the insurance industry, which have been modelled in a similar fashion in the Principal-Agent literature (see for example Goldsmith & Basak (2001)). The premium is a sum paid up-front, whereas the deductible is paid *ex post* – both serve to spread the risk between the principal and the agent.

⁷ For a mathematical proof that a risk averse agent being paid based in part on outcome would not accept a contract bearing all the risk, see Shavell (1979). Laffont and Martimort (2009) offer a good description of the intuition behind penalties, risk-bearing and the agent's participation in the contract.

avoid attention from CSOs, which would mean that CSO pressure would not be part of the agent's utility directly. If the principal is forward-looking, she can anticipate, *ex ante*, that the CSOs will exert pressure (even though the said pressure will only be exerted *ex post*). In that case, CSO pressure would be part of the principal's utility function at the outset.

With CSO pressure being within the principal's utility function (providing disutility), it indirectly affects the agent. For the principal to keep the same utility level, she has the following options: *Ex ante*, if a significant amount of CSO pressure is anticipated by the principal, then she can impose a stricter accreditation process upon her agent or offer him a smaller payment. *Ex post* (i.e., once the grant agreement is in place and money has started flowing from the donor to the grant recipient), as CSO pressure increases, she can impose a larger penalty (assuming that the agent is not performing at the agreed-upon level). These three options make the contract less attractive (riskier) to the agent, who may choose not to participate, as per the intuition offered in Shavell (1979).

If the agent is a larger or more visible organization, CSOs may choose to exert pressure on both the principal and agent. This is a plausible scenario, especially for certain accredited entities under the GCF, such as HSBC, Deutsche Bank and UNDP. In this context, CSO pressure would bring disutility to the agent, which would make him require a higher payment from the principal, at the outset, in order for him to be willing to take on the contract (assuming the agent anticipates the CSO pressure). The payment would need to compensate for the disutility generated by the CSO pressure for the agent to meet his reservation utility and accept the contract. If the agent cannot foresee the CSO pressure, he accepts the contract and the inclusion of the CSO pressure, *ex post*, reduces his overall utility. The agent, faced with this pressure, has the following options to regain his utility level: improve his effectiveness (i.e., achieving higher levels of α , ϕ and/or θ) to get paid more by the principal and avoid penalties for low performance, or reduce the cost of the MES (e.g., by increasing data collection efficiency). This is an appealing result for advocates of social accountability, as it shows that CSO pressure can drive project efficiency and effectiveness.⁸

The next section discusses how the principal and the agent's tolerance to risk can affect how contracts can be structured.

6 Impact of risk preferences

Another interesting area to analyze is the impact of risk preferences on the types of contracts that can be put in place between the principal and the agent. This is using the insights from Sinclair-desgagné & Spaeter (2016). Let us assume that the agent is risk averse, with a utility function that is increasing, strictly concave and thrice differentiable ($U_A' > 0$ and $U_A'' < 0$). The agent's risk aversion is simply when $U_A'' < 0$, whereas the intensity of this risk aversion is measured using the Arrow-Pratt ratio of absolute risk aversion (Arrow 1965; Pratt 1964), that we denote R_A for the agent: $R_A = -U_A'' / U_A'$.

As Ross (1981) argues, comparing risky situations requires measures that offer more insights than absolute risk aversion. Looking at prudence, which we denote D_A for the agent: $D_A = -U_A''' / U_A''$, gives us insights as to the amount of downside risk the agent would be willing

⁸ Social accountability is to be construed as a relationship where the account holders are external and lack formal authority vis-à-vis the account giver. The account holders, such as CSOs, exert influence over the account giver by using public criticism to create pressure, in the hopes that the account giver will change his/her behavior, or to motivate other actors in the accountability regime to sanction the account giver.

to bear (Kimball 1990).⁹ D_A informs us about how much the agent is willing to prepare in order to face inevitable risk. As Sinclair-Desgagné & Spaeter (2016) show, in order to analyze the extent to which the agent is willing to avoid risk altogether, another measure is required, linking the agent's absolute risk aversion and his absolute prudence: $D_A R_A = U_A''' / U_A' = d_A$. This gives us a measure of downside risk aversion (Modica and Scarsini 2005). This measure allows us to determine how much the agent will require in compensation to be subjected to an increased downside risk – the higher d_A , the higher the amount the agent will demand (Crainich and Eeckhoudt 2008). As such, if an agent has a large d_A , he will not be willing to accept a contract that includes a high penalty, as the downside risk is too much for him to bear, *ceteris paribus*. Similarly, if an agent has a large d_A , the principal will not be willing to provide the compensation level that will be sufficient to convince the agent to participate (i.e., the agent won't "play" if he doesn't get the pay that compensates the downside risk of a high penalty).

Prudence also influences the agent's willingness to participate when background risk is present. As Ligon & Thistle (2013) show, with a prudent agent, if background risk uncontrollable by the agent is present, the agent will seek out a contract where there is little difference in compensation whether poor or high performance is achieved (as measured by the outcome θ in our case). As such, it can be anticipated that the prudence of grantees will be important in the context of climate change financing, where mitigation, and especially adaptation outcomes, are subject to significant background risk. Potential grantees that are prudent would prefer not having too large a portion of their compensation payment contingent upon the achievement of a high outcome level θ , or at least not have this payment vary too much between high and low levels of θ . This may have more severe consequences for smaller grantee organizations, as they are more likely to be risk averse (Audia and Greve 2006; Dobrev 2001), which could lead international climate change financing institutions such as the GCF to disproportionately fund larger, less risk-averse organizations. In some cases, it may be possible that significant background risk could even lead large grantees to seek out contracts where there is little difference in compensation whether poor or high performance is achieved, for instance, if a given project is to be implemented in a fragile state, or in a country with poor institutions and weak macro-economic conditions.

7 Conclusions

The juxtaposition of the case with observable and unobservable effort allows to highlight how asymmetric information can increase the risk of low project performance for the donor in climate change financing, as the donor cannot directly observe how much effort the grantee is putting towards implementing the project. We also looked at how making grant payments contingent upon performance indicators related to the agent's activities and outputs, in addition to the climate change outcomes he achieves, can be beneficial if the performance indicators chosen are indeed positively correlated. This behooves the development of a solid theory of change for climate change projects.

We discussed formal accountability procedures such as *ex ante* accreditation and *ex post* penalties can influence recipient behavior and have a positive impact on project outcomes. We found that the accreditation process could lead the agent to demand a higher payment to

⁹ Formally, a prudent agent is one whose marginal utility is strictly convex (Kimball, 1990; Menezes, Geiss, & Tressler, 1980, as referenced in Sinclair-Desgagné & Spaeter 2016).

compensate for his “investment” in ex ante accreditation. In addition, when we put the accreditation process in the context of a set of agents seeking accreditation, we can see that it could lead to an overall cost increase for the donor, as climate change projects can only be proposed by entities that have been accredited, which enables those accredited entities to request higher compensation, as supply is thin.

The penalties were shown to help share the risk of poor project performance between the donor and the recipient. The penalties mean that the recipient has a personal stake in the achievement of climate change mitigation and adaptation results, and this risk-sharing arrangement therefore requires a larger compensation payment in order for the agent to be willing to participate. Moreover, we have seen that this hinges upon the risk profile of the project (including the overall risk environment, which can include macroeconomic trends, fragility of the country and the strength of the institutions that the project proponent needs to work with) and the level of risk the grant recipient is willing to take on and tolerate. As such, the donor needs to carefully consider the amount of risk she intends to impose upon her agent in the form of accountability requirements, including penalty schemes, to ensure that there is indeed a diverse set of entities willing to bid for the delivery of projects.

It is essential to put this paper into the broader context of aid effectiveness. The simplified relationship between the donor/principal and recipient/agent could lead readers to forget about the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness (OECD Development Assistance Committee 2008) and the importance of country ownership (as opposed to older-style development initiatives that were mostly donor-led). The donor-recipient relationship is in reality much more complex and subtle than what is described in the simplified analysis above: from the intricacies of international climate change negotiations and how developing countries can influence donors’ funding decisions based on their willingness to commit to greenhouse gas reductions, to the need for alignment between climate financing and country development plans. The use of the simplified relationship with a donor able to unilaterally dictate the terms of the climate financing contract serves only to isolate the specific accountability measures that we set out to analyze in order to more easily assess their potential impact.

The analysis and discussion above describe the relationship between a single principal (donor) and a single agent (recipient). This relationship is representative of the contracting between the GCF and one of its Accredited Entities, but can also be transposed to any relationship between a donor (bilateral or multilateral) and a recipient (developing country, implementing agency), and as such, provides broad-ranging insights. However, the relationship we describe is very much simplified. In reality, there is a “cascade” of accountability relationships in international climate change financing, with countries funding the multilateral institutions, who in turn funding implementing partners, who then sub-contract all or parts of the implementation. An area for future research would be to indeed attempt to model the complex accountability cascade using a multi-principal, multi-agent model, following Attar, Campioni, Piaser, & Rajan (2010), for instance.

Our analysis also takes for granted that the principal indeed takes her role of account holder seriously and does not hesitate to impose penalties for poor performance, for instance. This has been shown to often not be the case in practice and is one of the criticisms of using agency theory to analyze accountability issues (Schillemans and Busuioac 2015). The credibility and willingness of the principal to impose the accountability measures at her disposal are no doubt essential to the well-functioning of the accountability regime. Indeed, Basak and

Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen (forthcoming) discuss the political sensitivities involved in imposing heavy-handed accountability measures in the governance of the GCF.

Another area for future research would be to analyze how donors could further incentivize their grant recipients for the achievement of individual outcomes (e.g., carbon sequestration, climate resilience), using an approach similar to Thiele (2010), who used a multi-task principal-agent model to analyze how the varying abilities of an agent to deliver on certain tasks require different incentive contracts. Also, analyzing the role of trust as an element that has an influence on the principal and agent over the longer term would allow us see how agents can behave to increase their chances of receiving future funding, which is likely a strong incentive for agents to perform. As Broadbent et al. (1996) argue, trust and the building of long-term relationships can lead agents to better align their interests with those of the principal.

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